

Co-designed evidenced informed healthcare model and pathway for people living with suspected or diagnosed dementia in Scottish prisons.: Phase 3 Report

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice

*This work is supported by
The Dunhill Medical Trust
(Grant number RPGF/2006\236)*

 Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

About the study

This mixed methods study aimed to identify and develop new and effective ways to improve the health and well-being of the increasing numbers of older people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison.

Twenty semi-structured interviews were completed with staff to identify the current ways people with a suspected dementia were identified, referred, diagnosed and provided with post-diagnostic care in four prisons in Scotland with the largest number of people over 65 years (Phase 1).

The staff who participated included nurses based in prison healthcare centres, prison social workers, sessional support staff such as GPs, psychologists and forensic psychiatrists, Scottish prison service staff and staff contracted by the Scottish prison services to provide personal care.

Through interviews with a further four staff and five men living with diagnosed or suspected dementia and data from the healthcare records of the five men we gained an in-depth picture into their lived care experience (Phase 2).

This understanding informed the co-production of an evidence informed model of care and care pathway that inform and improve pre and post diagnostic care for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison (Phase 3).

Why this study is important

Prisoners with a suspected or diagnosed dementia are becoming an increasing concern to prison services and prison healthcare staff due to the complexity of their health and social care needs. There is very little known about this population or how they are cared for in Scotland. Suggestions for how to care for this marginalised group needs to move beyond speculation if we are to develop new effective ways to improve their health and well-being.

The number of people over 60 years of age trebled in UK prisons between 2002 and 2016. Recent data from England (Forsyth et al. 2020) suggested a much higher prevalence of dementia in prisons than found among community populations of the same age.

Improved ways of recognising and managing the increasing number of older prisoners with complex health needs including dementia is urgent. The consequences of not doing so may heighten fear and distress, reduce opportunities to access appropriate healthcare interventions and support, and violate human rights.

This study offers a model of care to develop evidence informed approaches to timely identification and diagnosis that would have many benefits to people with dementia and those who support them. It offers a co-produced evidence-informed care pathway that could serve as a tool for change that would enable the right care, at the right time, by the right people, and provide an opportunity to assess risk and plan care for the future.

About the phase 3 report

This report is the third in a series of five reports. This report focuses on the findings of phase 3 of the larger study described above. It presents the collaborative processes that involved a range of prison health care staff, prison staff, staff from community criminal justice and dementia organisations, people with lived experience of dementia and family carers. It also presents the co-designed outputs from those processes which include an evidence informed model of care and care pathway that serves as a tool for change to support people with a diagnosed or suspected in prison.

This report provides some concluding points from phase 3, the recommendations arising from the entire study can be found in the final report and the lay summary.

The other reports from the study can be found below:

1. Health and social care provision to people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in four Scottish prisons: **Phase 1 Report**
2. Case studies of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in prison: **Phase 2 Report**
3. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Project Report**
4. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Lay Report**

Co-produced approach

Before, during and after the project we liaised and consulted with over 120 people. The contact ranged from discussing and getting feedback on the research proposal, seeking organisational support for the project, securing access to study sites, working with staff to support data collection, holding update meetings with NHS prison healthcare and Scottish Prison Service senior management, holding five stakeholder workshops and sense checking email communications. We convened a Research Advisory group that consisted of twenty-four people who had lived experience of dementia and the criminal justice system, professionals involved in managing, leading on, or delivering the health or social care provision to people living in and transitioning out of prison and policy makers. The role of the Research Advisory Group which met on five occasions was to:

- ➔ Assist the research team by providing advice, contacts and introductions
- ➔ Advise, when appropriate, on technical or methodological aspects of the research
- ➔ Provide a forum for researchers to discuss the potential and the limits of the research
- ➔ Advise on the content and presentation of the research outputs.
- ➔ Provide feedback on interim and final reports
- ➔ Support stakeholder representation and participation at the stakeholder workshops

Throughout the phase 1 and 2 data collection period we invited all the prison and NHS staff we came in to contact with to participate in the planned stakeholder workshops that would take place after data collection was completed.

Stakeholder workshops

We held three in person action planning workshops involving thirty-eight people in early 2023. The aims of the workshops were to:

- ➔ Co-design evidence informed referral, diagnostic and post diagnostic healthcare pathway and stakeholders.
- ➔ Co-produce an evidence informed model for promoting later life wellbeing, and managing risks

Participants included staff from a variety of disciplines and grades from the Scottish Prison Service and NHS, as well as staff from criminal justice, social care and third sector community agencies who interface with those working and living in prison, and people with lived experience of the justice system and dementia.

Workshop 1

The first workshop was with twenty one NHS and prison staff who were involved in frontline service delivery. The research team presented the high-level findings from phase 1 and 2 that included the key themes from the data and two case study vignettes. We used Mentimeter© interactive presentation software to capture real time feedback and discussed the findings as a group.

To check if the findings had resonance, we asked '**Were there any surprises in the evidence presented?**

- All 21 responses indicated the findings presented all seemed very familiar, no surprises, the issues were well known.

To check if the data was capturing issues they encountered in practice, we asked '**Was there anything missing?**' The following observations and questions were noted:

- Was the Life History / perspective of families and person taken into account and recorded?
- Was there learning to be had from the collaborative work done previously in one prison and Alzheimer Scotland to raise awareness of dementia amongst prison staff, prisoners and families?
- Could people with cognitive impairment be part of the prison Equalities and diversity remit?
- The SPS and NHS have different systems (PR 2 and Vision), there is no access to each other's systems. How can we communicate better?
- Sometimes care plans are shared but not always, depends on establishment and consent gained. Would getting consent to share help this?
- The Multidisciplinary team (MDT) approach varies, all prison healthcare teams have multidisciplinary meeting but not all have interagency healthcare meeting that involve prison staff.
- It takes time to do referral and assessment well.
- Different establishments have different populations with different healthcare needs, the NHS staffing does not always reflect this.
- Missed educational opportunities? Can community NHS staff support education for SPS and NHS prison staff?
- Could there be agency leads for older adults and people with cognitive impairment? They could coordinate with one another and lead improvement.

Action planning workgroup

In small groups each group had 30 minutes to consider how the five objectives below could be achieved and operationalised. Prompts to support discussion included: what would enable this to be achieved? Is there one thing that would make a big difference? Who needs to do what, where and when?

Objective 1 - Develop a process for identifying and assessing prisoners with suspected cognitive impairment or dementia.

- ➔ Consider introduction of tailored cognitive screening for older people¹ in prison.
- ➔ Routinely get consent to share early to streamline the sharing of information.
- ➔ Record cognitive impairment in both NHS and SPS information systems.
- ➔ Training on GDPR and information sharing.
- ➔ Dementia training and education for all staff
- ➔ Have an NHS, SPS and Local authority adult services or HSCP lead that has responsibility for older adults/people with cognitive impairment.

Objective 2 - Develop a diagnostic pathway that includes input from specialist community services.

- ➔ Develop and implement a clear referral and care pathway with staff roles and responsibilities.
- ➔ Improve access to and links with community services and specialists (such as old age psychiatry, mental health OTs and older adult social work)
- ➔ Greater use of technology could enable more specialist services input into prison.
- ➔ Greater clarity of Social work role and responsibility. Criminal justice SW seem to be plugging gaps in adult and older adult SW services.
- ➔ Accountability and responsibility – identify NHS, SPS and HSCP leads to support coordination.
- ➔ Third sector provision, which often extends across local authority and health board boundaries, could be a source of support for staff, prisoners and families.

Objective 3 - Develop multidisciplinary care planning to address individual physical and mental and care needs.

- ➔ Clear and transparent communication and information sharing between NHS and prison staff. Training on GDPR and information sharing.

¹ There is no universally accepted definition of old age in prisons, the Scottish Prison service use the threshold of 55 years. These lower thresholds are based on evidence that suggests the health-related needs of prisoners are advanced by around 10 years, relative to people in the general population (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2021)

Objective 4 - Develop multidisciplinary care planning to address individuals needs for reasonable adjustments, and participation in social and recreational activities.

- Need access to staff with knowledge and skills to support social and recreational participation.
- Need access to staff with knowledge and skills to identify required reasonable adjustments.
- Greater shared understanding of confidentiality - what information can and can't be shared between agencies to support interagency working. Training on GDPR and information sharing.
- Improved interagency working and communication.
- People living in prison with dementia need to be identified in government strategies.
- Build design of new prisons needs to take account of ageing population. Money to retrofit and increase number of accessible cells.

Objective 5 - Develop multidisciplinary care planning to prepare and support individuals for progression and release

- Increase staff understanding the referral pathways within and at the interface of prison and the community.
- Ensure all staff know their roles and responsibilities.
- Improved partnership working (effective communication, information sharing)
- Identified multi agency leads with accountability and responsibility to support partnership working
- Social care cost increasing, need to support safe timely release.

Workshop 2 and 3

Workshop 2 and 3 followed and similar formats to that outlined above. The second workshop was with a range of NHS and prison staff who had strategic leadership and management roles and some staff involved in frontline service delivery. The third workshop was with people who had lived experience of dementia and or justice. The outputs of those discussions were then incorporated into the development of the model and care pathway.

Model and care pathway

Taking account of the evidence from this study, a recent English study (Forsyth et al 2020) and the priorities agreed in the stakeholder workshops we drafted a model and care pathway.

Workshop participants reviewed and provided comments on successive drafts of the model and care pathway. Both the model and pathway are underpinned by the [HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing](#) and the [National Health and Social Care Standards](#). Both adopt a human rights based and person-centred approach to care and treatment. The model and pathway sit within the recent recommendations made by the Mental Welfare Commission (2022) and the reports commissioned by the Scottish Government into the health and social care needs of prisoners (2021 and 2022).

The overarching aim of this model (Figure 1) is to represent the care principles to ensure the well-being of people with suspected or diagnosed dementia in prison and on release. It illustrates what needs to be in place to ensure an individual receives the right care, at the right time, in the right place, from the right people – those with the values, knowledge and skills to provide safe high-quality care and support.

Figure 1:
Model

HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing
 National Health and Social Care Standards: My support, My life
 Assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people with dementia and their carers (sign.ac.uk)

Figure 2: Care pathway (overleaf) provides all staff working in and at the interface of prison with a care pathway that can be used flexibly to support the implementation of current care standards. It is a resource for staff to refer to at any point in the pre and post diagnostic process. It is acknowledged that routine cognitive screening currently does not happen and would require planning and resource to incorporate it into current health assessment processes be they those conducted post admission or annually. It illustrates how identification, assessment, diagnosis, post diagnostic care and support for people with a suspected or diagnosed cognitive impairment or dementia can be operationalised and achieved.

This care pathway is not a standard or a guideline. It is a flexible resource that can be used to support the implementation of current standards such as the [HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: Health and Wellbeing](#), the [National Health and Social Care Standards: My support. My life](#) which adopt a human rights based approach. It recognises the need for all staff to be educated and supported to fulfil their role in preventing harm associated with prison life and promoting the health and wellbeing of all prisoners. See [SIGN 168](#) for clinical guidance on the assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people living with dementia.

Figure 2:
Care pathway

*The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is considered better than the MMSE as a global assessment tool (Roalf et al. 2013). It takes 10 minutes to complete. [Free one-hour online training with certification](#) for publicly operated health institutions.

*The ACE-III is a robust tool, often used in specialised assessments to assess for dementia and other neurological disorders. It takes 15-30 minutes to administer. [Free online training for NHS staff](#). Score of ≤82 indicates possible dementia, score of 83-88 possible cognitive impairment and need for specialist assessment.

Education for all staff in line with Promoting Excellence the national knowledge and skills workforce development framework

Informed level – all staff

Skilled level – staff with direct / substantial contact

Enhanced Level - staff with regular and intense contact who provide specific interventions / co-ordinate care and services

Expert level - staff who play an expert specialist role in care, treatment and support

Concluding points

1. Consideration should be given to resourcing the introduction of brief cognitive screening to those convicted and 55 years and over.
2. All staff administering cognitive screening should undertake the free online training.
3. Consent to share should be sought early to streamline the sharing of information within and between prison, NHS and partner agencies.
4. Education about ageing and dementia should be mandatory. All staff should be encouraged to use the dementia education resources in the NHS for Education Promoting Excellence Dementia Knowledge and Skills framework appropriate to their role.
5. The evidence informed co-produced care pathway should be made available to all staff working in and at the interface of prison to guide the processes for cognitive screening, referral, assessment and post diagnostic care.
6. Each prison should consider having a locally negotiated pathway for accessing an old age psychiatry and other appropriate specialist services for those under 65 years for those with a suspected dementia.
7. Those diagnosed with dementia should have a formal assessment of their needs by a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
8. An integrated person-centred package of care inclusive of the person and their family should be developed for these individuals to meet their biopsychosocial-spiritual needs within the prison setting.
9. Those diagnosed with dementia should have a named point of contact, professional or case manager who is a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
10. All prisons should consider implementing a monthly interagency healthcare meeting where these individuals are discussed and reviewed.
11. If advanced dementia care needs cannot be met within the prison setting, early consideration should be given to providing these in a more appropriate location.

References

Forsyth K, Heathcote L, Senior J et al., Dementia and mild MCI in prisoners aged over 50 years in England and Wales: a mixed-methods study. Health Services and Delivery Research, Vol 8, Issue 27. 2020 ISSN 2050-4349

Health and Social Care Standards: my support, my life. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/health-social-care-standards-support-life/>

HMIPs Inspecting and Monitoring: Standard 9: [Health and Wellbeing](https://www.prisoninspectorscotland.gov.uk/publications/inspecting-and-monitoring-standard-9-health-and-wellbeing) <https://www.prisoninspectorscotland.gov.uk/publications/inspecting-and-monitoring-standard-9-health-and-wellbeing>

House of Commons Justice Committee Ageing prison population. [Fifth Report of Session 2019–21 Ageing prison population](https://www.parliament.uk/publications/59400/1) (parliament.uk)

Mental Welfare Commission (2022). Mental health support in Scotland's prisons: under-served and under-resourced. <https://www.mwcscot.org.uk/sites/default/files/2022-04/PrisonReport-April2022.pdf>

Scottish Government (2021) Prison population: social care needs. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/understanding-social-care-support-needs-scotlands-prison-population/pages/2/>

Scottish Government (2022) Understanding the physical health care needs of Scotland's prison population. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/understanding-physical-health-care-needs-scotlands-prison-population/pages/4/>

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to all the organisations and individuals who enabled this research or participated in the study sharing their experiences and views.

This project was funded by the Dunhill Medical Trust [grant number RPGF/2006\236] and focussed on improving dementia care in prisons through co-designing an evidence informed dementia care pathway and other practical resources for staff working in Scottish prisons. The study commenced in Spring 2021 and reported in early 2024.

Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

About the Research Team

Dr Rhoda MacRae,
Principal Investigator and
Reader, Alzheimer Centre
for Policy and Practice,
School of Health and Life
Sciences, University of the
West of Scotland

Prof Debbie Tolson,

Co-investigator and Director, Alzheimer Centre for
Policy and Practice, School of Health and Life Sciences,
University of the West of Scotland

Dr James Taylor,

Co-investigator and Head of Division of Health and
Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Dr Kirstin Anderson,

Co-investigator and Lecturer in Criminology,
Edinburgh Napier University

Dr Natalie Chalmers,

Research Associate,
University of Edinburgh

Dr Tom Russ,

External Consultant and Director, Alzheimer Scotland
Dementia Research Centre, University of Edinburgh

Prof Lindsay Thompson, External Consultant and
Medical Director of The State Hospital, University
of Edinburgh

Glossary

Cognitive or Mild cognitive impairment, often known as MCI, describes a set of symptoms, that produce a decline in mental abilities. The difficulties caused by MCI are worse than would normally be expected for a healthy person of the same age. A person with MCI has mild problems with one or more of the following: memory, reasoning, planning or problem-solving, attention, language and visual depth perception. It is estimated that between 5 and 20% of people aged over 65 have MCI. It is not a type of dementia, but a person with MCI is more likely to go on to develop dementia (Alzheimer's Society, 2023).

Dementia is an umbrella term describing a progressive neurodegenerative syndrome caused by illnesses such Alzheimer's disease that cause structural and chemical changes to the brain. The changes most notably affect memory, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgement. Consciousness is not affected. The impairment in cognitive function is commonly accompanied, and occasionally preceded, by deterioration in emotional control, social behaviour, or motivation (WHO 2017). As the illness progresses the trajectory is not fixed nor predictable, and people can and do live for months and years with advanced dementia-specific palliative care needs (Reisberg et al 2006) before they reach the stage of dying with dementia.

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a short cognitive screening tool.

6-item cognitive impairment test (6CIT) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination, third revision (ACE)- III, is a more comprehensive cognitive screening tool.

Residential area is the term this report uses for describing the areas in the prison where people in prison were accommodated. The prisons had different names for these areas including hall, wing, unit, flat.

dementiainprisons.com

**Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice**

If referring to or using material from this publication please use the following citation
MacRae, R, Tolson, D, Taylor, J, Anderson, K, Chalmers, N, Russ, R and Thompson, L (2024).
The health and social care of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in
prison: Phase 3 report

